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O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETI
JIZZAX FILIALI

**KOMPYUTER ILMLARI VA
MUHANDISLIK TEXNOLOGIYALARI**

**XALQARO ILMIY-TEXNIK
ANJUMAN MATERIALLARI**

**TO'PLAMI
2-QISM**

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ONLINE MIND MAPS AS ONE OF THE MEANS OF MASTERING FOREIGN LANGUAGE VOCABULARY

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Abstract: Structuring information is important when learning vocabulary in a foreign language. Using mind maps will help students navigate new vocabulary more easily. Online mind map platforms can make this task easier.

Keywords: online service, education, mind maps, students, online platforms, foreign language.

Using mind maps is an effective way of working with vocabulary in English lessons, as they provide good systematization of the material. Mind maps are the development of a famous scientist, lecturer and consultant on issues of psychology of learning and problems of thinking T. Buzan. It was he who spread the idea of using mind maps as an effective way of working with information [1].

In the process of studying foreign language vocabulary, it is recommended to use various methods of working with mind maps. This can be a joint creation of maps in the lesson together with the teacher, pair or group work, individual compilation, as well as independent development of maps at home with subsequent checking by the teacher.

In teaching a foreign language, mind maps can be used for a variety of purposes: for visual representation of complex lexical material, for drawing up retelling plans, for organizing brainstorming in the lesson, as a support for conducting discussions, as a support for oral monologue or dialogic statements. However, the most effective way to use mind maps is to introduce new lexical units, practice lexical material, primary consolidation, and repetition. It is possible to use mind maps to control foreign

language vocabulary [3]. This tool can be used both for homework and for preparing for tests. When students use a mind map, they become more confident when working with new lexical material, as they allow them to better structure and contribute to better memorization of vocabulary that may seem too difficult if the teacher uses a traditional approach to building a lesson. Mind maps also allow for better development of critical thinking, helping students find non-standard approaches to solving certain educational problems. Visually presented lexical units significantly facilitate the understanding and memorization of new foreign language vocabulary. The peculiarity of the human psyche is that bright and unusual images are better fixed in our memory. It is on this principle that the effectiveness of using mind maps is based. This tool helps not only in memorizing new lexical units, but also in systematizing the knowledge already known to students. This approach creates a solid foundation for further learning of a foreign language.

The essence of the method of using mind maps is that the main concept is identified, from which tasks, ideas, individual thoughts and ideas necessary for building a specific project then branch off. Just like the main one, all smaller branches can be divided into several more branches [1]. Due to the use of various images and colors, any information is perceived, analyzed and remembered much faster.

Among the advantages of mind maps, one can highlight their versatility: they can be adapted to various subjects and topics. Unlike traditional methods, such as notes or tables, mind maps provide an integrated overview of topics, showing the interaction between concepts [2]. The main advantage of mind maps is visualization, as well as structuring, which allows you to better absorb information than text.

The development of a mind map begins with defining the topic, which occupies a central place. Branches branch out from this topic, each containing key aspects related to the main topic. For example, in a foreign language lesson, you can create a mind map that will show not only new words from the new topic, but also the correct pronunciation of these words, translation, and photos for better understanding.

There are a huge number of online services for creating mind maps. These platforms can offer templates and visual elements, allowing students to play with the structure and design of their maps. This approach makes the learning process more fun. With their help, absolutely everyone will find a suitable tool for their needs. Let's consider some of the most popular services.

"Coggle" is a service for creating mind maps that is suitable for beginners. Its main feature is the ability to create fairly simple mind maps. The teacher, as well as students, can easily share their maps with others for collaboration and discussion. Its main emphasis is on the simplicity and visual appeal of the maps. With the help of "Coggle", you can quickly and easily add images and links directly to the maps. The distinctive feature of Coggle is the ability to collaborate in real time, which allows students and teachers to interact easily. This service is used in various fields, including education. The teacher and student take their notes and share them with each other.

"Coggle" has the ability to use various templates and tools to create a mind map, they help to visualize any topic more simply and clearly. Also in this service you can add images and links. This makes the material more interesting and informative. This is useful for students who need to present complex concepts visually.

The "XMind" platform offers many useful features for the teacher and student, including templates and styles for designing maps. "XMind" offers various display modes, for example, "tree", which allows the teacher to choose a more convenient way to visualize information for the student. Unlike "MindMeister", "XMind" can work without Internet access. In addition, the platform supports many formats, including PDF and Microsoft Word, which makes it convenient for use in the educational process.

"MindMup" - this service allows you to create mind maps that are visible to all users and share them online, which opens up the opportunity for joint discussion of educational material. This platform supports collaborative editing, which allows the teacher and students to work effectively on lesson topics and projects.

"MindMeister" is also suitable for collaborative work between a student and a teacher, it allows you to create mind maps in real time. This online service is suitable for both introducing new vocabulary and reinforcing the covered vocabulary or organizing brainstorming in class. You can also work in a group or in pairs in this service. This allows several students to simultaneously edit one map, which greatly simplifies the process of collaborative work in class.

The choice of a suitable platform for creating a mind map depends on the goals and objectives of the lesson. As we can see, most services allow group work on a mind map, collaborative editing. This contributes to the widespread use of mind maps in the educational process. It is important to remember that the best tool is the one that meets the individual needs of the student and teacher, and allows you to optimally solve the goals and objectives. Creating mind maps requires a careful approach, which can greatly facilitate the learning process and assimilation of information. Although there are no uniform rules for creating such maps, special platforms offer many templates and ready-made mind maps, which makes the learning process more labor-intensive. Also, updating mind maps plays an important role. This allows you to maintain the relevance of information, provides the opportunity to add new ideas.

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